

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Inclusion Lab

ESIL Environmental Data Science Needs Assessment Report

Prepared by Megan Littrell, Anne Gold, Kelsey Johnston, & Emily Ward

University of Colorado Boulder

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Introduction

Program Description

The Environmental Data Science Innovation and Inclusion Lab (ESIIL, www.esiil.org) serves as a data science center of excellence and synthesis center that facilitates collaboration across large, diverse teams through the ESIIL Network. ESIIL brings together a diverse community of environmental and biological data scientists to turn environmental and biological data into actionable understanding and knowledge toward a more sustainable society. The center activities support ESIIL's mission: *“Empower an inclusive and diverse community to accelerate continental-scale environmental data science (EDS)”*.

This report includes the outcomes of a **Needs Assessment** conducted in the first year of the ESIIL data science center development. The goals of this evaluation work are to identify the needs, priorities, and goals of the Environmental Data Science community and identify paths to strengthen the center's growth and development.

Evaluation Methodology

Data for the needs assessment were gathered at two time points over the course of the first year of the project. First, the evaluation team sent a survey to the ESIIL leadership team about needs and priorities for ESIIL in October 2022. Three team members responded to the online survey. The same questions were discussed during a facilitated leadership team discussion in December 2022. During the discussion, team members added their responses to the prompts in an online Google Jamboard and these were discussed further as a group. Responses from both data sources were combined and grouped into general themes. Next, the leadership team's responses were used to generate questions and response options for a survey to be distributed widely to members of the developing Environmental Data Science (EDS) Community. These needs assessment questions were embedded in an online pre-survey that was given to attendees before the first annual ESIIL Innovation Summit in May 2023.

ESIIL Program evaluation is co-led by Anne U. Gold, Megan K. Littrell, and Emily Ward. This study has been approved by the University of Colorado Institutional Research Board (IRB) Protocols 22-0266 and 23-0162. Funding for this work was provided by the National Science Foundation (NSF, Award #DBI-2153040). Any opinions, findings, conclusions, or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the NSF.

Executive Summary

Highlights

ESIL Leadership Team Needs Assessment Findings

The ESIL Leadership team identified several EDS community priorities and needs to overcome challenges and barriers. There was overlap in priorities and challenges identified for the broad EDS community and within the team members' respective areas of content focus within EDS (e.g., Cyberinfrastructure; Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning; Diversity, Equity and Inclusion), summarized below:

Key Priorities for the EDS Community Included:

- Establish EDS as an academic and applied discipline;
- Develop EDS skills training and education resources;
- Advance open science and infrastructure to support open science;
- Foster inclusive growth of the EDS community, with emphasis on indigenous data sovereignty and data ethics;
- Diversify and expand the EDS workforce;
- Support collaboration and innovation in diverse teams through team science best practices;
- Advocate for environmental and climate justice; and
- Facilitate research addressing societal environmental challenges

Needs Identified to Overcome Challenges and Barriers Included:

- Improving infrastructure, accessibility, and resource allocation;
- Improving access to training and educational resources;
- Addressing the mismatch in value and reward systems across diverse sectors;
- Fostering enhanced transdisciplinary and cross-cultural collaborations through cultural competency and collaboration skills training;
- Establishing a unified identity, vision, and values within the EDS community;
- Cultivating a cohesive EDS community culture and trust-building with community partners; and
- Providing essential training resources to facilitate growth and ensure inclusive community membership.

Important Content Focus Areas for Data Synthesis in the EDS Field:

- Training in leadership, cultural competencies, and transdisciplinary collaboration skills to lead working groups and work effectively with various communities.
- Training resources to foster a culture of inclusivity and cultural understanding within the EDS community.
- Clearly defining EDS and cultivating a culture that promotes interdisciplinary and cross-sector collaboration.
- Fostering community interaction, bridging different groups within EDS, and creating opportunities for shared learning and collaborative support to encourage innovative thinking.

- Defining synthesis within EDS, establishing common language, and providing access to tools and skills required for effective synthesis, including data skills training and knowledge of various datasets.
- Preparing cyberinfrastructure for data-related tasks and streamlining compute capabilities across experience levels to support EDS activities.
- Nurturing a new generation of individuals who value EDS work, possess the necessary skills, and can train future generations to contribute to the field effectively.

ESII Innovator Summit Attendees EDS Needs Assessment Findings

Top priorities for the EDS community

The top five EDS Community Priorities identified by the Summit attendees included:

- Expand access to **training** in data skills and on EDS applications (**77%** of respondents)
- Focus EDS on **solving environmental challenges** for society, including climate justice (**63%** of respondents)
- Diversify the EDS workforce (**57%** of respondents)
- Broaden access to **infrastructure** to work with big data (**57%** of respondents)
- Create an **inclusive and welcoming culture** in the EDS field (**54%** of respondents)

Key Challenges or Barriers to the EDS Community

The top five challenges for the EDS Community identified by the Summit attendees included:

- Limited or Lack of **data skills** (**59%** of respondents)
- **Disciplinary boundaries** (i.e., language barrier for technical discussion) (**51%** of respondents)
- Limited offerings or insufficient access to **EDS skill training** (**39%** of respondents)
- Lack of or insufficient access to necessary **Cyberinfrastructure** (**38%** of respondents)
- Lack of **transdisciplinary collaboration** (**38%** of respondents)

There were several varied, open-ended responses provided to capture other challenges not included in the response options. These are summarized as:

- Newcomers to the field of EDS struggle to find guidance, training paths for specific EDS skills, and opportunities to engage in research. There is a lack of awareness about what EDS involves that is compounded by environmental scientists not identifying as data scientists.
- Institutional reward systems often hinder the interdisciplinary work needed for EDS. Data quality and trust concerns cut across disciplines, and there is a lack of understanding of open data sources.
- Inclusivity and diversity issues relate to insufficient training in creating inclusive environments, low diversity within the field, and inadequate funding and reward structures for diversity and inclusion efforts.
- Data sovereignty and ethical considerations are significant, with open data seen as potentially dangerous.

Recommendations

The community needs align with those identified by the leadership team, particularly in areas of improving EDS skills training and working toward improving diversity, equity, and inclusion within the field through leadership training and institutional support for these efforts (i.e., financial incentives and rewards systems). There is also a need to continue working to better define the Environmental Data Science field, establish a common set of values and ethical practices, and welcome newcomers and those who may not strongly identify with the field or community of EDS. As ESIL and the EDS community grow, it will be important to continue reflecting on these needs and how well they are being addressed.

Leadership Team Needs Assessment

Top priorities for the overall EDS community

The following themes emerged from the leadership team's survey and discussion responses. Verbatim responses are included below each theme.

Establishing EDS as an Academic and Applied Discipline

- "Institutionalize EDS in interdisciplinary networks, journals, societies, etc."
- "Establishment of professional societies and journals."
- "Institutionalize EDS in interdisciplinary journals, networks, research associations, etc."
- "Development of new organizational forms (such as ESIIIL) to act as institutional infrastructures for advancing research and creating dense social networks."
- "Building connections across sectors and user communities (broadly defined)"
- "Catalyze collaborations between natural and social scientists working with environmental data."
- "Identify who is IN the EDS community and which specialties in the natural and social sciences are most active so that we know what 'interdisciplinary' or 'synthetic' means."

Advancing Open Science & Infrastructure for Open Science

- "Bridging the gap in public perception and scientific knowledge by practicing open science."
- "Open science across the EDS community"
- "Provision of data infrastructures"
- "Access to data and compute resources for all"
- "Capacity to work with big data - ML, cyberinfrastructure, data science, etc."

Positively Impacting Environmental and Climate Justice

- "Climate Justice"
- "Environmental justice & big data"
- "Research agenda vs. social change"

Supporting Research Efforts to Solve Environmental Challenges for Society

- "Cascading Hazards"
- "Research to meet society's environmental challenges"
- "Applied science focus"
- "Providing science to inform solutions to critical (local-global) environmental change problems."
- "Adapting to a changing world"
- "Global environmental change as it relates to how humans interact with the world"

Diversifying and Expanding the EDS Workforce

- "Focus on applied science as a way to get students ready for the workforce/diversifying the workforce"
- "Diversification of the workforce"
- "Increasing the size and diversity of the workforce"
- "Diversification of workforce"
- "Inclusivity in EDS"

Developing EDS Training and Education Resources

- “Create advanced EDS education resources that include AI/ML applications, published as OER”
- “Development of valid/reliable EDS education assessment + evaluation tools”
- “Continued capacity building to teach/learn EDS at smaller MSIs”
- “Data and computer science skills”
- “Edu Research Q: How are EDS scientists developing (acquiring?) EDS skills to remain active in the community as researchers?”
- “Training in data skills (open education)”

Other Science Topics

- “AI for Earth,”
- “Continental-scale ecology.”

Priorities for Leadership Members’ Content Focus within ESII

The following themes emerged from the leadership team’s survey and discussion responses. Verbatim responses are included below each theme.

Supporting Collaboration and Innovation in Diverse Teams through Team Science Best Practices

- “What group dynamics enable groups to unleash productive capacity of diversity”
- “Enhanced understanding of organizational conditions that lead to successful teams”
- “Improved understanding of how to facilitate effective production of creative scientific knowledge in teams and organizations.”
- “Training for the community in team science best practices”
- “Improved understanding of how team environments, compositions, and dynamics shape the quality and content of scientific knowledge and practical outcomes of synthesis”

Solving Environmental Challenges for Society and Promoting Climate Justice

- “AI ML: Forecasting Cascading Hazards”
- “AI ML: Grounding in Climate Justice”
- “Research to meet society's environmental challenges”

Fostering the Development of EDS as an Inclusive and Ethical Field

- “Inclusivity in the EDS field and the ESII network”
- “Helping to educate the EDS community on Indigenous Data Sovereignty and data ethics.”
- “Tension between academic reward structures/timelines and community/application partner reward structures/timelines”
- “Creating a culture that is supportive and welcoming to encourage broad participation”

Providing EDS Skills Training and Education Resources

- “Training in data skills”
- “Training for the community in open science best practices”
- “Helping lead/organize Stars program (design curriculum, develop schedule w/ faculty partners, coordinate w/ eval team, mentor projects)”

Promoting Open Science & Infrastructure for Open Science

- “Lowered barriers to use of scalable compute (costs, access, bandwidth, experience, etc.)”
- “Streamlined access to big data to reduce time for data wrangling and munging and accelerate culturally-relevant analytics”
- “Data and compute access that spans gradients of experience, access needs, and privacy needs”
- “Provide the most advanced cyberinfrastructure in the world to the EDS community, becoming the envy of all other sciences”

EDS Community Challenges or Barriers for Collaboration

The following themes emerged from the leadership team’s survey and discussion responses. Verbatim responses are included below each theme.

Need for Better Infrastructure, Accessibility, and Resource Allocation in EDS

- “The lack of the infrastructures and human resources to support and sustain a growing scientific field.”
- “CI unevenly distributed / accessible”
- “Limited resources, no strong institutional homes in terms of societies, journals, etc.”
- “Knowledge of other groups in other disciplines, research centers, etc. working on relevant topics”

Mismatch in Value and Reward Systems held within Communities and across Academic and Industry Sectors

- “External value systems (funding, merit metrics, etc.)”
- “Mismatch between rewards and incentives in the academic/industry/community goals. This is an issue in most community-based or applied research.”
- “Maybe look at literature in the engaged scholarship space with ideas for bridging the reward/incentive gap?”
- “Tension between academic reward structures/timelines and community/application partner reward structures/timelines”

Need for Improvements in Transdisciplinary and Cross-cultural Collaborations

- “Cross cultural communications”
- “Building capacity for cross-cultural/diverse world view productivity and skillful interaction.”
- “Variable confidence levels by contributors”
- “Not knowing how to contribute in diverse groups”
- “Respect for variable needs to participate”
- “Disciplinary boundaries”
- “Disciplinary boundaries, i.e. language barrier for technical discussion, or that different team members focus on different aspects, as opposed to a big research team”
- “Helping people through the journey of new things/discomfort/presumptions/productive conflict (where it happens)”

Need to Establish a Common Identity and Vision for EDS as a Community

- “No clear definition EDS”
- “Assumptions of ‘how it should be’”
- “Lack of integrative research agendas, questions, joint phenomena of interest”

- “That it doesn't have an identity as a single community. This is one of the most important functions of ESIL, in my view”
- “Cultivating an identity of community”

Need to Establish the Culture of EDS as a Community and Build Trust Across Communities

- “Cultivating a sense of community”
- “Not a barrier, but a need: Build mechanisms for the leadership to transparently model the culture we intend to build. Attention to culture at all scales of the project.”
- “Again-an imperative, not a barrier: Building trust with communities we haven't worked with before.”
- “lack of accountability and inequitable power dynamics”

Need for Training Resources to Support Growth and Inclusive EDS Community Membership

- “We need to level the playing field in terms of skills and access to resources to ensure that the ESIL community is diverse and inclusive.”
- “Training to develop EDS skills can be hard to come by (exclusive to broad segments of the population)”

Challenges or Barriers within Leadership Members’ ESIL Content Areas

The following themes emerged from the leadership team’s survey and discussion responses. Verbatim responses are included below each theme.

Need to Establish EDS as a Community with Common Values

- “Reaching a common value system and sense of belonging to this as a community”

Need for Improved Access to Training and Education Resources

- “Access to teaching and learning materials”

Need for Improvements in Data Ethics, Security, and Trust-Building

- “Building trust around security of data and compute”
- “Ensuring ethical data science as we open up to reduce barriers to more domain experts without knowledge or ethical practices”

Need to Develop Cultural Competencies and Transdisciplinary Collaboration Skills to Support Effective and Diverse ESIL Working Groups

- “Developing good selection criteria for working groups”
- “More control over initial conditions of collaboration than direct influence on group dynamics”
- “Diverse groups of people can lead to better scientific outcomes, but it also introduces challenges and people need to have skills in interdisciplinary collaboration.”
- “Transmitting our ideas, values, leadership philosophy to group leaders and participants in ways that endure across the lifecourse of the group and beyond”
- “Developing cultural/interpersonal competencies for everyone that support interdisciplinary and diverse teams to work effectively”

Needs for ESIIIL-Specific Improvements for Events, Collaboration, Research, and Training

- “ESIIIL subteam structure”
- A member of a subteam noted that they have not seen collaboration challenges yet because there are the small number of team members. (Paraphrased to keep data de-identified)
- “We need to encourage folks to apply/come to the Innovation Summit who span disciplines in the environment, computer/data, and social science fields!”
- “Currently don't have AI/ML EDS edu materials that we use in our teaching so coming up with those (from scratch?) could be a challenge. Will need to partner w/ [AI] team”
- “Deciding which aspects of team dynamics to investigate.”

Need for Resources & Human Capacity within ESIIIL

- “Time and person power needed to gather and analyze the team science data are the main challenges/needs.”
- “Funding mechanisms for access to scalable compute”

Content Focus Needs for Data Synthesis in the EDS Community

The following themes emerged from the leadership team’s survey and discussion responses on the areas of content focus needed to move the EDS community toward data synthesis. Verbatim responses are included below each theme.

ESIIIL Leadership Training on Cultural Competencies and Transdisciplinary Collaboration

- “Leadership training for folks from underserved communities (e.g., ESIIIL Leaders training) to lead working groups, proposal teams, etc.”
- “Leadership training for us to better work with these people/communities!”
- “Cultural intelligence training (not just for Tribal but what is CQ broadly)”
- “Training and practice in inter/multi/trans disciplinary collaboration”
- “Lots of need for scaled resources/training materials/feedback loops to help people achieve the inclusive culture we want. Some available now, some not.”
- “Training/learning around cultural understanding”

Establishing a Definition of EDS and a Culture of Transdisciplinary Collaboration

- “Clear definition of EDS”
- “Increase culture of interdisc/cross sector collab”

Building a Sense of Community in EDS and Bringing People Together for Learning and Innovation

- “Community interaction to help create bridges.”
- “Bringing people together to brainstorm”
- “Various groups need to made aware of each other and where their skills, interests, abilities intersect”
- “Time together”
- “A coming together around shared learning and a culture of support that empowers both people and innovative thinking”

Defining Synthesis and Providing Support through Training and Educational Resources

- “Clear definition of what we mean when we say 'synthesis'”
- “Need for common language to break down barriers to siloed disciplines”
- “Access to tools and skills needed to synthesize”
- “Training and dissemination of synthesis methods - meta analysis, qualitative comparative analysis, etc.”
- “Data skills training for all.”
- “Need for knowledge of different datasets and how to wrangle and ‘munge’”
- “TRAINING”

Building Cyberinfrastructure

- “My understanding is that the cyber-infrastructure is ready to create data cubes. Synthesis, analysis, and fusion can be done via AI, in Y2 and 3.”
- “Streamlining use of compute capabilities across experience levels”

Workforce Development

- “A new generation that values such work and has the skills to conduct it and train the third gen”

Leadership Team Partners for Data Science and Synthesis

The following themes emerged from the leadership team’s survey and discussion responses around who to partner with on data science and synthesis in EDS. Verbatim responses are included below each theme.

Researchers in Social Science, Technology Studies, and Team Science

- “Researchers in soc of science, science and tech studies, science of team science”
- “I have collaborated with [names redacted] on synthesis team research”

Industry Partners Using Data Science for Informed Decision-making, Compute Resources, and Workforce Development

- “Industry people bringing data science to workforce”
- “Industry people providing compute resources”
- “Industry includes non-profit and for-profit”
- “Industry people using data science to inform decisions/provide services for informing decisions”

Education Institutions Serving Diverse Communities and EDS Educators

- “MSI, HSI, HBCU, TCU, etc.”
- “Undergraduates, faculty from Tribal Colleges & Universities (TCUs)”
- “Other EDS educators”

Data Providers, Application Partners, and Socio-Environmental Groups

- “Data providers, applications partners, and other socio-environmental groups.”
- “Data providers - NASA, NEON, LTER, USGS, NOAA, etc.”
- “I personally have connections with data providers, applications partners, and other socio-environmental groups.”

Other Partners Focusing on Integration of EDS, AI, CI, and DEI

- “AI should interface with both CI and DEI”
- “We define environmental data science as the integration of data sciences with environmental sciences... read proposal definition.”
- “So far within ESIIIL: Evaluation/Tribal Engagement/Leadership/Education/CyberInfra Externally: students and early career scientists/faculty with aligned interests.”
- “CI, DEI”

Groups, Communities, and People to Include in ESIIIL

The following themes emerged from the leadership team’s survey and discussion responses on consideration of “Who is not yet at the table” within EDS and who ESIIIL needs to include. Verbatim responses are included below each theme.

Industry Partners

- “Industry”
- “industry”

City Planners & Engineers

- “City planners and engineers- those who construct the social-ecological systems in which we live and interact with nature”
- “Engineers, city planners,”

People working Social Science, Political Economics and Ecology Science Fields

- “Many potential contributors in human geo, soc, psych, anthro, political economics, political ecology, etc.”

Community and Tribal Partners and Educational Institutions (MSIs, Community Colleges)

- “Citizen stakeholder groups”
- “Our tribal connections are strong (and will continue to grow), but we need to partner with other MSIs more closely to move towards serving the whole nation.”
- “Community college faculty and students”

Computational Sustainability Community Members

- “Computational Sustainability community (E.g. Tom Dietterich and Carla Gomes)”

Others Involved with Related initiatives and Scholarship

- “Foundation initiatives - e.g. Google has one about increasing Diversity in STEM”
- “The philosophers, particularly ethicists and epistemologists”
- “Who’s not here yet: EAB, more non-academic interested parties.”

Dimensions of Diversity to Define Diversity within the EDS Community

The leadership team also outlined ideas on how to define diversity within the EDS community. Verbatim responses are included below. These contributions and further discussion with the DEI team contributed to the development of demographic questions included in the EDS community needs assessment.

- “institutional, disciplinary, cultural, gender, methodological, data type, age, sectorial”
- “access, experience, and security”
- “Disciplinary, racial/ethnic, career stage, sector (e.g., academic vs. industry), gender”
- “Any difference that makes a difference for collaborating participants in terms of their expectations, norms, values, ability to cooperate, etc.”
- “Geographical as global environmental change disproportionately affects the global south.”

Remaining Questions to inform the Leadership Team’s Work within ESIL

Below are the leadership team’s verbatim responses indicating their remaining questions:

- “Who are we forgetting/who have we not yet thought of?”
- “what major disciplines and specialties within the life and social sciences are most active in the environmental data science community?”
- “AI/ML EDS applications”
- “Connecting more with AI for ecology”

ESIL Innovation Summit Participant Needs Assessment

The following responses were collected as part of the 2023 ESIL Innovation Summit pre-survey. The findings from the ESIL leadership team's needs assessment were used to develop questions and response options for this needs assessment with the broader EDS community.

Top priorities for the overall EDS community

Respondents selected 3 or more priorities from a list generated from the leadership team needs assessment.

EDS Community Priorities	Percentage
Expand access to training in data skills and EDS applications	77%
Focus EDS on solving environmental challenges for society, including climate justice	63%
Diversify the EDS workforce	57%
Broaden access to infrastructure to work with big data	57%
Create an inclusive and welcoming culture in the EDS field	54%
Improve access to EDS education resources, including AI and Machine Learning application	48%
Expand access to training on ethical data practices	46%
Increase public awareness and acceptance of Open Science	43%
Establish EDS as an academic and applied discipline	41%
Cultivate an identity of an EDS community	21%
Other. Please specify.	6%

Responses given as “Other” highlighted several important aspects for the EDS community, including the need to attract talented individuals with technical backgrounds, build trust with Native American and Indigenous communities, establish data standards, expand access to available data through a dedicated platform, improve communication of EDS work to the general public, address Indigenous Data Sovereignty concerns, recognize the ongoing nature of data work, and conduct a survey of EDS research. Overall, respondents find it challenging to prioritize among these important elements.

Key Challenges or Barriers for the EDS Community

Respondents selected 3 or more challenges from a list generated from the leadership team needs assessment.

Challenges	Percentage
Limited or Lack of data skills	59%
Disciplinary boundaries (i.e., language barrier for technical discussion)	51%
Limited offerings or insufficient access to EDS skill training	39%
Lack of or insufficient access to necessary Cyberinfrastructure	38%
Lack of transdisciplinary collaboration	38%
Challenges in cross-cultural communications with community partners	35%
Tension between academic approaches and application partner needs or approaches	33%
No strong institutional home for EDS (e.g., professional societies, departments, journals)	32%
Not enough high-quality teaching and learning materials	32%
Variable confidence level by contributors and partners	28%
Lack of trust around security of data	27%
Not enough Environmental Data Scientists	23%
Other. Please specify.	13%

There were several open-ended “Other” responses provided for this question. These responses can be grouped into the following themes:

Challenges in Entering the Field:

- Newcomers find it challenging to navigate the wealth of information available in the field of EDS due to a lack of clear institutional guidance.
- Lack of an obvious training path or direction for entering the EDS field.
- Uncertainty on how to get involved in research and the EDS space if not currently working in it.

- Some individuals are not sure about how to engage with the EDS community as newcomers.

Awareness and Identity Issues:

- Environmental scientists often don't identify themselves as data scientists.
- There is a lack of awareness about what EDS entails.

Skills and Training:

- Lack of data management skills.
- Training materials for complex data science applications are not designed for scientific programmers.
- Uncertainty about how to get involved in EDS research for those not currently working in the field.

Financial and Institutional Concerns:

- The field lacks strong financial support and incentives for scientists engaged in EDS and Open Science.
- Institutional and organizational reward systems and cultures often hinder interdisciplinary work in EDS.
- Compensation for EDS practitioners in academia is generally lower than in industry.

Data Quality and Trust:

- Trust in the quality of data across disciplines is a concern.
- Understanding of existing open data sources and their correct usage is lacking.

Inclusivity and Diversity:

- Lack of training in fostering inclusive environments.
- Pre-existing low diversity in the field.
- Funding and reward structures in academia that do not do enough to foster inclusion and retention.
- The research community does not always invite community partners or stakeholders to collaborate.

Environmental and Climate Justice:

- The intersection of data and justice is a critical concern.
- Desire for increased applicability of EDS in addressing environmental and climate justice issues for both humans and non-human entities.

Data Sovereignty and Ethical Concerns:

- Data Sovereignty is a significant concern.
- Open Data is seen as widely accepted but potentially dangerous.

Practical Application and Integration:

- Limited practical application of EDS to daily work.
- Bridging field observations with environmental data science is not common.

Additional Feedback from Summit Attendees

Summit attendees were asked to share any additional feedback they had about EDS priorities and necessary EDS opportunities and training. Responses include the following themes and key points:

- **Training and Technical Skills:**
 - Many participants highlighted the need for training in EDS-related skills, such as grant writing, data analysis, and working with large datasets.
 - There is a call for training on when and why to use advanced tools like ML/AI, as well as promoting general data literacy and big data methods.
 - Several respondents mentioned the importance of incorporating technical training into academic programs.
- **Access and Equity:**

- Participants expressed concerns about disparities in access to research funds, training, and cyberinfrastructure between nations. Addressing these disparities is seen as crucial.
- There is a desire to value data science as a means to solve environmental problems, ensuring that society recognizes its importance.
- **Data Literacy and Awareness:**
 - Lack of familiarity with acquiring and utilizing large datasets is identified as a significant challenge. This highlights the importance of improving data literacy among practitioners and researchers.
 - The importance of integrating Indigenous Knowledge into EDS to create culturally acceptable solutions is emphasized.
- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration and Networking:**
 - EDS scholars often work across disciplines and sectors without a strong institutional home. Networking and collaboration with partner organizations are suggested as ways to provide resources and connections.
 - Building open-access datasets, especially in areas like public health, is recommended to advance EDS research.
- **Global Reach and Development:**
 - Participants stress the importance of making EDS a global subject and improving participation from developing countries. This involves addressing infrastructural and funding challenges.
 - The need for valuing applied and multi-disciplinary projects within the field of data sciences is highlighted.
- **Data Quality and Study Design:**
 - Ensuring data quality and addressing bias is a concern. Participants recommend focusing on study design and its interface with data science algorithms.
 - Some mention mistrust around data use, even when it legally belongs to the data provider.
- **Cultural Awareness and Respect:**
 - One respondent suggested fostering a deeper connection and respect for the organisms being studied in EDS, acknowledging their contributions and seeking permission to use their knowledge.

Appendix. Evaluation Instruments

Leadership Team: ESIL Needs Assessment Survey

Please help us complete this ESIL Needs assessment leadership team survey. We are using this survey to generate a brief survey to send out to the larger Earth Data Science (EDS) Community. Please take 15-20 min to share what you know about the EDS community with an EDS content focus that you represent in the ESIL leadership team.

Informed Consent Researchers at the University of Colorado Boulder a needs assessment to collect information about needs, interests and practices of the larger Earth Data Science (EDS) community that ESIL is/will be serving. To develop a survey for the larger EDS community, we are asking all ESIL team members to fill out this longer survey with open-ended questions, that will allow us to build a tight and targeted survey instrument for the broad EDS community. Responses to this 10-15 min survey will be used to create a community needs assessment survey. This research is funded by the National Science Foundation. We expect about 25 people will complete this survey. Your participation in this survey is voluntary. You may choose to withdraw at any time and it will not be held against you. Survey responses will be collected anonymously. You will not be paid to take part in this survey. There are no anticipated risks to taking the survey. Your participation in the survey will benefit the ESIL team to learn more about the needs of the EDS community. If you have questions or concerns, you may contact the Evaluation Principal Investigator, Anne Gold at anne.u.gold@colorado.edu or the University of Colorado Boulder IRB office at 303-735-3702 or irbadmin@colorado.edu. Thank you for your time and input.

Authorization: I have read this information about the research/evaluation study. I know that participating in this research is voluntary. I choose to be in this research study. I know that I can withdraw at any time.

Do you agree to participate in the research/evaluation study as explained above in this consent form? By selecting "Yes," you provide your electronic signature and agree to participate in this research study. Select "No" if you would not like to participate.

Yes

No

What describes best your content focus in ESIL?

AI & Machine Learning

Team science

Education

- Tribal Partnerships
- Cyberinfrastructure
- Data Analytics
- DEI
- Strategic Planning
- EDS Community
- Other _____

Toward the goal of developing a decadal research agenda for the Earth Data Science (EDS) community, please share what you see as the **top priorities for the overall EDS community**. Please list all you can think of but indicate which ones are the top five.

Now that you have thought about the priorities for the entire community, please share what you see as the **priorities for your specific content focus** within ESIL (e.g. CI, DEI, AI/ML). Please list all you can think of but indicate which ones are the top five.

What are the challenges and barriers you see for the **overall EDS community** to effectively work together?

What are the challenges and barriers you see **within your content focus within ESIL** (e.g. CI, DEI, AI/ML) to effectively work together?

Within the context of your content focus within ESIL (e.g. CI, DEI, AI/ML), what needs (e.g., resources, training, structures, people) exist to move the broader EDS community toward data synthesis?

ESIL is working on a definition of diversity for the work of the center. What dimensions or aspects of diversity should be included in defining diversity within the EDS community?

Who do you partner with around data science and synthesis within your EDS content focus within ESIL (e.g. CI, DEI, AI/ML)?

Who are the big players and main communities in the data science synthesis field within your content focus? Please name organizations, groups or key people.

Who is not yet at the ESIL table that we should reach out to? Please name groups, communities, or specific people.

What else do you want to know about the EDS community to inform your work within ESIL?

2023 ESIIIL Innovation Summit Pre-Survey

ESIIIL Innovation Summit participants were selected based on their ability to help build the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community of the future. **Understanding the thoughts and opinions of Innovation Summit participants is therefore crucial.** Please fill out the information below to the best of your ability.

Please consider the following definition of Environmental Data Science when answering the questions in this survey: *We define EDS broadly to include any work where big data is used to drive discovery, solutions and science to understand our environment. It is highly transdisciplinary, including aspects of the natural and social sciences (that explore the environment and human interactions) and data sciences.*

[Note: The full survey included more questions, summarized in other reports. The questions below are those that pertain to the EDS Needs Assessment conducted at the ESIIIL Innovation Summit.]

We would like to understand the top priorities and key barriers you see in the development of a vibrant and inclusive EDS community.

What do you see as the TOP PRIORITIES for the overall Environmental Data Science (EDS) community? Please select at least three.

- Establish EDS as an academic and applied discipline
- Increase public awareness and acceptance of Open Science
- Broaden access to infrastructure to work with big data
- Expand access to training in data skills and on EDS applications
- Expand access to training on ethical data practices
- Improve access to EDS education resources, including AI and Machine Learning application
- Cultivate an identity of an EDS community
- Create an inclusive and welcoming culture in EDS field
- Diversify the EDS workforce
- Focus EDS on solving environmental challenges for society, including climate justice
- Other. Please specify. _____

What are the key challenges and barriers you see for the overall Environmental Data Science (EDS) community? Please select at least three.

- Lack of or insufficient access to necessary Cyberinfrastructure
- No strong institutional home for EDS (e.g., professional societies, departments, journals)
- Tension between academic approaches and application partner needs or approaches
- Disciplinary boundaries (i.e., language barrier for technical discussion)
- Lack of transdisciplinary collaboration
- Limited or Lack of data skills
- Limited offerings or insufficient access to EDS skill training
- Not enough high-quality teaching and learning materials
- Not enough Environmental Data Scientists
- Challenges in cross-cultural communications with community partners
- Variable confidence level by contributors and partners
- Lack of trust around security of data
- Other. Please specify. _____

Please provide any additional feedback on EDS priorities and necessary EDS opportunities and training.
